

TECHNIQUES OF WORK ON THE SIMULATOR OF THE LINE " HEYVUS " FOR THE DEVELOPMENT OF THE ABDOMINAL PRESS AND BACK EXCELLENT MUSCLES

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Annotation. The article is devoted to the main points of the practical use of the heyvus training complex, considered on the example of a simulator for the development of abdominal muscles and back extensors. The peculiarity of the simulator is that it allows you to work out any part of the abdominal press or muscles of the lumbar back safely for the user's spine in different modes, including the mode of urgent passive muscle relaxation. The stages of work on the simulator are considered, and a diagram of the simulator device is also given.

Keywords: simulator, abdominal muscles, back muscles, extensors, non-inertial loader, hyperactivity, load

Heyvus training complex , which we will consider as an example of a simulator for the development of abdominal muscles and back extensors. The peculiarity of the simulator is that it allows, due to the precise coaxial adjustment of the axis of rotation of the lever and the point on the line of flexion of the spine, as well as due to the use of a non-inertial elastic loader, it is safe for the user's spine to work out any part of the abdominal press or muscles of the lumbar back in different modes, including in the mode of urgent passive muscle relaxation. In this case, all individual settings are recorded as values on the scales. Working in the passive muscle relaxation mode improves the blood supply to the lumbar spine, reduces the hyperactivity of the vertebrae and intervertebral discs, which occurs due to the underdevelopment of the musculoskeletal apparatus of the lumbar spine [1].

Work on the simulator consists of the following steps:

1. Preparation for work. The minimum load is set on the rack of loaders 1 with hooks for rings. In this case, one rubber ring is left on the hooks. The lever of the loading mechanism 2 is moved to the desired position using the angular position switch of the lever 3. The drum 4 is set to the middle position using the clamp 5 [2]

2. Placement of the user on the simulator. The knee rest 6 is retracted to the farthest position from the user. The user turns around with his back to the simulator and sits on the seat 7. The feet are placed on the support platform 12 [3] .

Drawing. The scheme of the simulator device: a) general view; b) phase separation unit - close-up.

3. Axis setting. The first setting is recommended to be carried out with an instructor. The user sits in such a way that the spine is in line with the axis of rotation of the lever. In this position, the back 8 is pressed against the lower back and fixed

with a clip. The seat height is adjustable so that the user can comfortably bend back. The knee stop 6 is pressed against the knees and fixed with a clip. Then the user leans on the back of the lever 9, grasps the handles 10 to bring the previously separated shoulder supports together. One slow extension or flexion of the body is performed. In this case, the lower back is pressed against the back throughout the entire range of motion. The back of the lever rests on the back in the same place throughout the working stroke. If this is achieved, the scale values are recorded for further use, if not, a more accurate adjustment of the axis is performed. With the help of stop 11, the limitation of the back deflection is set in accordance with the flexibility of the lumbar spine of a particular user [4].

4. Performing an exercise. For the abdominal muscles - the user holds the handles 10 with his hands and from the starting position performs the flexion of the spine at the desired speed. For the back - using the lever angle switch 3, the lever is moved forward to the desired angle (according to the flexibility of the user's lumbar spine) and from the starting position performs a back extension.

5. The main modes of operation of the simulator [5] :

- Power;
- speed-strength;
- a set of muscle mass;
- work on endurance, including strength and speed, on explosive strength;
- on the elasticity of the muscular-ligamentous apparatus, on the flexibility of the spine;
- restorative, relaxation;
- as well as aerobic and anaerobic.

Intended areas of application:

- fitness clubs;
- amateur and professional sports;

- children's sports;
- health-improving and therapeutic physical culture;
- rehabilitation after injuries and operations;
- recovery in the postpartum period;
- special physical training for professions and activities;
- prevention of occupational diseases of the musculoskeletal system, etc.

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